

Another fragment (PAM 44.102 frg. 12) of 4Q334 (4QOrdo)

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4QOrdo, in its final publication by Glessmer (DJD XXI), is comprised of nine small fragments, which were grouped together on account of their script, content, and physical appearance. The name “Ordo” was given on account of its contents: it lists the songs and words of praises for each night and day of the month (hence, Qimron gave the descriptive title לוח שירות ותשבחות). For a discussion, see also Ben-Dov. The schema of the list seems to be

1. on the umptieth (day) in it (of the month) (e.g. בעשרה בו):
2. in the night: so many songs (e.g. בלילה שירות שמונה) and so many words of praises (e.g. דברי תשבחות עשרים)
3. in the day: so many songs and so many words of praises.

Among the unidentified fragments of PAM 44.102 (IAA Plate 196), frg. 12, containing only a few letters, fits the fragments of 4Q334 both with respect to script and to content. The editors misread the traces (DJD XXXIII, 306). One should read:

ודברי	1
ה בו	2

PAM 44.102 frg. 12: screenshot from PAM 43.674

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285453>

photo Najib Albina

According to the schema of 4QOrdo, ודברי would have been followed by תשבחות, and the ה before בו would have belonged to an ordinal. The trace of the letter preceding ודברי would have been the last letter of the ordinal with the word שירות. It might be either the foot of *taw* or the left bottom end of the right stroke of *ayin*.

The script of 4Q334 varies, both in letter forms, thickness of the strokes, and neatness of the writing. The few letters of PAM 44.102 have relatively thick strokes, are written quite neat, and fit with the script. Note also the characteristic small word space between ה and בו.

Glessmer offered two options for the reconstructions of 4Q434. The evidence of the PAM 44.102 frg. 12 is very limited, but the η before \beth , indicates it was one of the cardinals between three and nine (day “ten” is mentioned in 4Q334 frg. 3), so that the fragment would have belonged to the first part of a month.

Bibliography

- Ben-Dov, Jonathan. *Head of All Years: Astronomy and calendars at Qumran in their Ancient Context*. Leiden: Brill, 2008, esp. 139-40.
- Glessmer, Uwe. “Ordo.” In *Qumran Cave 4, XVI: Calendrical Texts*. Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXI. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001, 167-94.
- Pike, Dana M., and Andrew C. Skinner. *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXXIII. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001.
- Qimron, Elisha. *The Dead Sea Scrolls: The Hebrew Writings*. Vol. 2. Jerusalem: Yad Ben-Zvi, 2013.

Photographs

For PAM 44.102 see <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284999> and DJD XXXIII, pl. XLI

The identified fragment is also photographed on

PAM 44.081: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285092>

PAM 43.674: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285453>